

Thus it appears that the copper(II) complexes are four coordinate while the nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes are six coordinate, and in all of them the pyrrolidonate ion is monodentate, coordinating through >CO group alone and its negative nitrogen simply neutralises the charge of the metal(II) ion.

The copper(II) complexes are paramagnetic with their μ_{eff} values lying in the range of 1.83-2.16 B.M. The appearance of a band between 14.00-18.00 kK with two shoulders at ~ 12.50 and 10.50 kK is indicative of the planar stereochemistry of the complexes. The assignments of the band may be ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ (14.00-18.00 kK), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ (12.50 kK) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ (10.50 kK), respectively. The position of the main band, directly equal to Dq, occurs at ~ 1400 cm^{-1} in the pyridine and picoline complexes and at ~ 1800 cm^{-1} in diamine complexes and correlates well with the position of these ligands in spectrochemical series.

The μ_{eff} values of nickel(II) complexes lie in the range of 3.00-3.65 B.M. indicating high spin octahedral structures. The three bands in the electronic spectra at 25.50, 18.00 and 11.50 kK due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) transitions, respectively and the Dq values of 1150 cm^{-1} are also characteristic of an octahedral structure^{1,2-15}. The ν_3 and ν_2 bands are both split into two components due to the lowering of symmetry on account of the presence of different ligands around the metal.

The cobalt(II) complexes also possess high spin octahedral structures as the μ_{eff} values lie around 4.70 B.M. In the diffuse reflectance spectra, two sharp bands due to ν_3 and ν_1 transitions are observed at 20.00 and 8.00 kK. The shoulder at 15.50 kK is the ν_2 transition as expected. The splitting of the ν_3 transition into two components, one at 20.50 kK and the other at 18.50 kK has been attributed to the lowering of the symmetry of the complexes owing to the coordination of different ligands to cobalt(II). The Dq and B values are around 900 and 1010 cm^{-1} supporting the pseudo-octahedral structures for the complexes¹⁶⁻¹⁹.

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Synthesis and Structural Studies of Some First Row Transition Metal Complexes of Salicylidene Ethyl Carbazate

R. C. AGGARWAL*, N. K. SINGH and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 23 February 1982, revised 14 December 1982, accepted 30 March 1983

ALTHOUGH a number of papers are available on the transition metal complexes of salicylidene alkyl dithiocarbazate and its N- or S-alkyl substituted derivatives^{1,2}, there is no previous report on transition metal complexes of salicylidene derivatives of alkyl carbazates. In view of our earlier work on transition metal complexes of salicylidene derivatives of hydrazine and picolinoyl hydrazine^{3,4}, it was of interest to undertake preparative and structural studies of the salicylidene ethyl carbazate (SEC) complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II). The results of these studies are presented here.

Experimental

Preparation of salicylidene ethyl carbazate (SEC): Salicylidene ethyl carbazate, *o*-OHC₆H₄CH=N-NH-COOC₂H₅, was prepared by reacting salicylaldehyde with ethanolic solution of ethyl carbazate in $\sim 1:1$ molar ratio. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallized from CHCl₃, m.p. 133°. (Found: C, 57.24; H, 5.48; N, 13.15; N₂H₄, 15.24. C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₃ requires C, 57.69; H, 5.76; N, 13.48; N₂H₄, 15.38%). Ethyl carbazate required for the above preparation was obtained by the reaction of diethyl carbonate and hydrazine hydrate following the literature procedure⁵.

Preparation of the complexes: The complexes Cu(SEC-2H)₂.H₂O and M(SEC-H)₂ [M=Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) or Zn(II)] were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of SEC and aqueous solutions of the appropriate metal chloride in 1:1 and 2:1 molar ratio, respectively and raising the pH of the reaction mixture to about 6-7 with dil. NH₄OH solution. The complexes thus precipitated were filtered, washed with CHCl₃ and dried *in vacuo*.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND GENERAL BEHAVIOUR OF THE SEC COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	m.p. °C	Molar conductance (DMF) at $10^{-3} M$ (mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$)
		Metal	N_2H_4	Nitrogen			
Mn(SEC-H) ₂	Light yellow	11.62 (11.72)	18.40 (13.64)	11.55 (11.94)	5.88	> 300	10.5
Co(SEC-H) ₂	Orange	12.70 (12.42)	18.60 (18.53)	11.90 (11.84)	4.9	> 300	8.0
Ni(SEC-H) ₂	Green	12.34 (12.42)	18.65 (18.54)	11.52 (11.86)	3.33	> 300	—
Cu(SEC-2H).H ₂ O	Dark green	21.95 (22.1)	—	9.26 (9.74)	1.78	242 ^d	14.5
Zn(SEC-H) ₂	White	14.06 (13.64)	13.26 (13.35)	11.76 (11.68)	Diamag.	> 300	15.0

d=decomposes

Physical measurements :

Experimental details pertaining to analysis and electrical conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral measurements of the complexes were the same as described earlier⁹. Analytical data, molar conductance and magnetic moments of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data show that SEC forms 1 : 1 deprotonated complex Cu(SEC-2H).H₂O with Cu(II) and 1 : 2 deprotonated complexes of the type M(SEC-H)₂ with Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) or Zn(II). While the Cu(II) complex loses water at 140-150° and then decomposes at 242°, the other complexes neither melt nor decompose upto 300°. The complexes are insoluble in water and organic solvents such as ethanol, acetone, chloroform and DMSO but, with the exception of Ni(SEC-H)₂, are soluble in DMF. The values of molar conductance in DMF for these complexes fall in the range 8-15 mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, indicating their non-ionic nature⁹.

Magnetic moments : The magnetic moments of 5.88 B.M. for Mn(SEC-H)₂, 4.9 B.M. for Co(SEC-H)₂, and 3.33 B.M. for Ni(SEC-H)₂ indicate that all the complexes are spin-free with octahedral/tetrahedral geometry around Mn(II) ion and octahedral geometry around Co(II) and Ni(II) ions. The μ_{eff} value of 1.78 B.M. for Cu(SEC-2H).H₂O corresponds to one unpaired electron and is normal, giving no specific information about its stereochemistry.

Electronic spectra : The spectrum of Co(SEC-H)₂ shows a broad band at 9050 cm^{-1} and a strong band at 19000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_2) transitions in octahedral environment of Co(II)⁷. Using the above values of ν_1 and ν_2 , Dq, B, β , β^0 and LFSE work out to be 1070 cm^{-1} , 715 cm^{-1} , 0.73, 27% and 102.3 kJ/mole, respectively.

Ni(SEC-H)₂ shows two bands at 10800 and 16660 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively

characteristic of octahedral geometry⁸. ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.54) falls in the range of octahedral Ni(II) complexes⁸. Using the above values of ν_1 and ν_2 , Dq, B, β , β^0 and LFSE have been calculated giving the values of 1080 cm^{-1} , 690 cm^{-1} , 0.65, 35% and 155 kJ/mole, respectively.

Cu(SEC-2H).H₂O yields one broad band at 16400 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the envelope of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{2g}$, 2E_g transitions assuming square planar geometry of the complex⁹.

Infrared spectra : The ir spectrum of the ligand (SEC) yields two bands at 3450 and 3260 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$ and $\nu(\text{N-H})$ modes, respectively. The absence of these bands in the ir spectrum of Cu(II) complex suggests the loss of protons from phenolic as well as imino groups of the ligand. The deprotonation of the latter group occurs via enolisation of the keto group as shown later.

$\nu(\text{C-O})$ band occurring at 1710 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand disappears in the spectrum of Cu(SEC-2H).H₂O and suffers a negative shift of 40-80 cm^{-1} in the spectra of other complexes indicating the destruction of the keto group via enolisation in the Cu(II) complex and coordination through carbonyl oxygen in the other complexes. The destruction of C=O group in Cu(II) complex is further supported by the presence of a new band due to $\nu(\text{NCO})$ at 1530 cm^{-1} .

$\nu(\text{C=N})$ and $\nu(\text{N-N})$ bands observed at 1625 and 1050 cm^{-1} , respectively in the ligand appear around 1605-1615 and 1065-1075 cm^{-1} regions in the spectra of the complexes. A negative shift of 10 to 20 cm^{-1} in $\nu(\text{C=N})$ and a positive shift of 15-25 cm^{-1} in $\nu(\text{N-N})$ ¹⁰ modes in the spectra of the complexes suggest that the azomethine nitrogen is involved in coordination.

The band at 3520 cm^{-1} in Cu(II) complex may be assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of water molecules. The occurrence of a band at 800 cm^{-1} shows coordinated nature of the water molecule in the above complex¹¹.

The non-ligand bands occurring in the region 290-300 cm^{-1} and 320-340 cm^{-1} may be tentatively

assigned to $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ modes, respectively ¹²⁻¹⁴.

The infrared spectral studies thus indicate that SEC behaves as a uninegative tridentate ligand in all the complexes except in $Cu(SEC-2H)_2 \cdot H_2O$ where it is binegative tridentate.

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Complex Formation Between Some Transition Metal Ions and Phenetsal

V. K. JAITLEY and B. S. PANNU

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University,
Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 1 October 1982, accepted 19 March 1983

PHENETSAL (*p*-acetylaminophenyl salicylate) is analgetic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic and tuberculostatic. Because of these characteristics, the studies on the metal ion complexes of phenetsal were undertaken^{1,2}. The stabilities of the complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with phenetsal are reported here. Bjerrum-Calvin^{3,4} *pH* titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁵ has been used for the study,

Experimental

Phenetsal was synthesised by reported method⁶. It was purified and dissolved in absolute alcohol to get a 0.02 *M* solution.

The metal salts used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. Their solutions were prepared in water and standardised to 0.01 *M*. The aqueous 0.05 *M* HClO₄ was standardised against a standard alkali. One molar aqueous solution of NaClO₄ was used to maintain the required ionic strength. Carbonate free 0.1 *M* KOH was used for *pH* metric titrations.

A Sisco made water thermostat, type TBS, fitted with an electric stirrer, heater and toluene regulator, was used to maintain the temperature constant. The *pH* metric titrations were run with a Systronics *pH* meter, model 322-1 fitted with glass and calomel electrodes assembly. The following three titrations were performed with the standard alkali.

- A. Mineral acid alone.
- B. A + ligand solution.
- C. B + metal ion solution.

The total initial volume in all titrations was 20.00 ml in alcohol-water 70 : 30 (v/v). As the titrations were carried out in alcohol-water system, the correct values of *pH* were obtained by appropriate correction⁷. The curves were plotted between the volume of alkali added and *pH* reached.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\bar{n}$ and *pL* were calculated by Irving and Rossotti method⁸. The values of stability constants were calculated by linear extrapolation and half $\bar{n}$ methods⁸. The average values of stability constants in log units are given in Table I. The values of thermodynamic stability constants were obtained by plotting $\log k_a$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolating to zero ionic strength. The values of free energy change (ΔG) associated with complex formation were obtained by the relation

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K$$

These values are also given in Table I. The stability of the complexes are in the order $Cu^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Mn^{2+}$. This order can be explained on the basis of increasing second ionization potential and electronegativity values and decreasing ionic radii in the same transition metal series. The crystal field stabilization energy plays important role in enhancing the stability of the complexes in the case of ions other than Mn^{2+} . The stability order found here agrees with the Irving and Williams order⁹.

The values of stability constants record a decrease with rise of temperature and ionic strength of the medium. Low temperature, therefore, is favourable for complexation.